

	<i>ndhF-rpl32</i>	<i>atpB-rbcL</i>	ITS
<i>D. micrantha</i>	10 of 13	12 of 13	9 of 13
<i>D. virgata</i>	4 of 5	4 of 5	5 of 5
<i>D. maximiliana</i>	7 of 7	6 of 7	6 of 7
<i>D. costaricensis</i>	1 of 2	0 of 2	2 of 2
<i>D. ciliata</i>	2 of 2	2 of 2	2 of 2
<i>D. expansa</i>	3 of 3	3 of 3	2 of 3
<i>D. tenera</i> subsp. <i>tenera</i>	5 of 5	5 of 5	3 of 5
<i>D. tenera</i> subsp. <i>durangensis</i>	3 of 3	3 of 3	1 of 3
<i>D. aptera</i>	3 of 3	3 of 3	3 of 3
<i>Palmerella debilis</i>	2 of 2	2 of 2	2 of 2
<i>Lobelia</i> spp.	7 of 18	6 of 18	16 of 18
<i>Trachelium caeruleum</i>	1 of 1	1 of 1	1 of 1
<i>Campanula medium</i>	0 of 1	1 of 1	1 of 1

TABLE S1. Number of specimens out of total available where data were obtained.